

MODERN MARKETING STRATEGIES IN ENHANCEMENT OF FOOD PRODUCTS BRAND VALUE

Khodjiev Ibrahim Ikramovich

*National Social Protection Agency under the President of the Republic of
Uzbekistan*

Head of Namangan region administration

Email: mm29090709@gmail.com

Abstract: Marketing strategies for increasing brand value of food products are highlighted.

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The lack of experience of food production enterprises in Uzbekistan in creating national brands and turning them into global brands requires expanding the scientific and methodological basis of using new approaches, tools and brand concepts in their marketing activities. In this regard, taking into account the current budget constraints and the influence of the competitive environment, it is on the agenda to effectively organize the brand development process with maximum consumer and added value and to develop theoretical and methodological approaches to increase brand value. These conditions require conducting scientific research aimed at improving the methodology of evaluation of the brand of food products and increasing its value.

The scientific-theoretical aspects of solving the problems of food production and marketing, including the research of the formation of a brand of food products, are reflected in the works of many foreign scientists. In this regard, Assel G.[1], Churchill G.A., Brown T.J., Kotler Ph.[2], Keller K.L., Setiawan I., Karatajaya H., Malhotra N.K., Kennedy D.[3], Praet V.D.[4], Salenbacher The scientific works of J. Traindl A. [5], Trout J., Doyle P. have become classic works. Despite the significant contribution of these foreign scientists to marketing, marketing strategy and brand formation, the scientific methodological foundations of food brand formation and evaluation have been created.

In the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States, Bagiev G.L.[6], Tarsevich V.M., Bulanov A., Veselova A.O., Godin A.M., Golubkov E.P., Grechin E.Yu.[7]], Makashyov M.O., Pravda P., Rozhkov I.Ya., Kismerishkin V.G. such

scientists conducted research. Although the scientific-theoretical aspects of brand theories and consumer goods brand formation and branding strategy development are covered in these studies, the issues of marketing strategy development for milk and milk products brand formation are not studied.

In scientific literature, especially in the scientific literature of Uzbek scientists, the concept of trade mark has been used more often. In our opinion, such approaches do not fully reveal the content and essence of the brand. A brand is defined as a manufacturer's brand. In many cases, middleman or seller's brand (retailer brand, store brand or private label) is used only in the sales process, so it is appropriate to use it in the research process. However, in certain circumstances, "brand", "trademark" or "prestige" (image) should be used as synonyms only when the meaning is correct.

The phrase "local brand" was born from the presence of different regions of the region, especially the production, storage and consumption of milk and milk products, the requirements of state standards for these products, and the need to take into account their characteristics when entering the world market.

In order for a trademark or sign to become a brand, based on the definitions discussed above, one conclusion can be reached - when the team takes its place in the consumer's mind, and due to effective communication, its differences from competing goods become added value for consumption. The difficulty of drawing a line between a trademark and a brand is shown by the studied literature, conducted marketing research and practice analysis. In some literature, the minimum awareness level in the mind of the target audience is 20%, some 30%, others 50%. For a local brand, in our opinion, such recognition should be at least 70 percent. Studies show that an enterprise or product must be active in the market for at least 5 years in order to become a brand.

In other words, every brand can be considered a trademark, but not every trademark can be a brand. Legal registration of a trademark cannot ensure its competitiveness.

Brands, like goods, go through a life cycle: market entry, growth, maturity, decline. Of course, if the effective use and management of the brand is organized, it will ensure their long-term viability and stability. For example, Lipton, Coca-Cola, Levi's and other brands can be cited as sustainable brands. According to broader approaches to the term brand, clarifying the concept of a local brand is important for branding theories. National brands represent the Republic of Uzbekistan in the international market. So far, an attempt has

been made to see the brand of the company (entrepreneurs) or their products at the scale of the domestic market. For this reason, the use of the expression "Local brand" is scientifically and methodologically appropriate. Of course, in the market of milk and dairy products, it becomes a "national brand" only when it is exported, like fruits and vegetables. These circumstances require the creation of scientific-methodical, practical and theoretical aspects and methodological foundations of the formation of local brands in the market of milk and dairy products.

In foreign economic literature, the brand is considered as a strategic resource that ensures a stable competitive advantage of the enterprise. Sustainable competitive advantage is defined as "Productivity improvement is a set of actions that are carried out by using a specific strategy to achieve a long-term advantage." The phrase sustainable competitive advantage was used for the first time in 1985 in the works of M. Porter. [

Branding refers to specific methods of influencing a target market segment's attitude toward the brand and its overall reputation.

A.M. According to Yanovsky, "Branding is the science and art of leveraging a brand for long-term advantage." [18]

David Ogilvy, one of the leading scientists in the field of advertising, suggests using a set of intangible characteristics of a brand to define the concept of branding: its name, packaging, price, history, reputation and advertising methods. [19]

Uzbek scientist I. Khotamov defines that "Branding is a modern technology of marketing, which includes the processes related to the creation of new goods and trademarks, placing them on the market, and absorbing them into the minds of consumers." [20]

Of course, during the formation of the digital economy, the appearance and content of a stable competitive advantage is changing.

For example, M. Porter in his writings indicated the presence of 5 threats to competitiveness in the market segment: "In all branches of the economy, regardless of whether they operate in the domestic or foreign market, the content of competition is represented by five forces...".

In the five forces of competition, the brand can perform a specific function and have different effects on the competitiveness of the enterprise. The main task of the brand is to express the attitude towards the influence of consumers.

A strong brand allows the company to reduce the influence of customers. The demand for branded goods is more stable than for unbranded products ("Generics") and the price elasticity is lower. A consumer's propensity leads to an increase in repeat purchases. As seen in practice, a 5% increase in consumer propensity leads to a 100% increase in profit from that customer. A higher (premium) price for a branded product provides an opportunity to make a higher profit. In other words, the attractiveness of the brand serves to bring net additional income.

Brands are the second most important enterprise asset after human resources. In Great Britain, Hong Kong and Australia, if they are taken into account as intangible assets in the balance sheet, in the USA they will enter the reputation of the company ("Good will") and serve to increase their market value.

The local brand also helps the manufacturer to enter other markets with new products. For example, the "Nestle" brand in the Uzbekistan market has the opportunity to expand its position in the water, confectionery, and other food markets, in addition to the milk and dairy products market. The success of this company can be determined by the trust in it. Such a situation shows the possibility of achieving the transition from one market to another without excessive expenditure on advertising and other promotional activities.

Studies have shown that the role of a local brand in improving the effectiveness of a product or service is high. A more marketing approach will also help promote the local brand. In modern marketing, a product is considered as a means of satisfying human needs. The stronger the local brand, the more advantages it gives its owners over their competitors. Especially in milk and milk products, as the number of producers increases, it becomes difficult for consumers to switch from well-known brands to other products. The manufacturer wants the consumer to choose his product among the competitors. In this regard, the division of goods into groups also plays an important role in marketing.

In the processes of using brand strategies in Uzbekistan, although the marketing concept of "brand" is present in the minds of consumers, clear directions have not been defined regarding the main concepts of modern marketing. There are almost no concepts of how enterprises evaluate the brand of goods accepted by the consumer, and the processes of forming the value of consumers to brands provide maximum market opportunities. These situations determine the need to describe the concepts of the brand in relation to each other.

Depending on the characteristics of the consumer market of Uzbekistan, the uniqueness of branding is explained by the following:

- Since the brand awareness culture of Uzbekistan consumers is not high, creating a new brand and using it in the market does not require a lot of time and financial resources. For example, if 20-50 million dollars are required for the promotion of one brand in European countries, it can be limited to 3-5 million dollars in the conditions of Uzbekistan;
- due to the rapid saturation of our domestic market, consumers do not have time to develop a preference for one or another brand, because new goods tend to be updated day by day;
- consumer confidence in foreign products, especially in the food sector, tends to decrease. For example, in milk products, while the product of the "Nestle" company was almost a monopoly, we can list dozens of local producers;
- in the domestic market, the consumer's trust in the manufacturer's trademark has not yet been fully established;
- when creating a local brand in the domestic market, there is a need to spend an expensive advertising company, and consumers have high confidence in advertising;
- consumers' understanding of the local brand is formed in their minds mainly through three factors: the country of manufacture, the attractiveness of the packaging and the brand. For this reason, these three factors of product offering should be taken into account in the formation of local brands;
- national values, customs and other local characteristics are taken into account in advertising. For this reason, the need for personalization of the brand is important, especially for the market of Uzbekistan. Taking into account the unique historical and cultural characteristics of each region and region are the main features that should be taken into account in the formation of a local brand.

A brand's values can be seen based on the emotional outcomes experienced by consumers when using the brand. When creating the value of the brand, attention should be paid to the factors that shape consumer values, consumer preferences, and their inclination to the brand.

In other words, trademark, trademark and brand are very close concepts, but there are specific differences between them. This should be taken into account when building a brand.

References:

1. Churchill G.A, Brown T.V. Basic marketing research, -Thomson, United States, 2010; Kotler Ph. Marketing essentials. –Prentice Hall, United States, 2019;
2. Kotler Ph., Setiawan I., Kartajaya H. Marketing 3.0: From Products to Customers to the Human Spirit. – wiley, 2012.; Malhotra N.K. Marketing research an appled orientation. – Prentince Hall, United States, 2016;
3. Kennedy Dr No B.S. Guide to Brand – Building by Direct Response – Entrepreneur Press, 2014,
4. Praet V.D. Unconscious Branding. How neuroscience can empower marketing. – Prentince Hall, USA, 2012,
5. Salenbacher J. Creative personal branding. –BIS Publishers, 2013,
6. Bagiev G.A., Tarasevich V.M. Marketing – St. Petersburg: Peter, 2012;
7. Grechin E.Yu. Brand creation. –SPb.: Peter, 2018